

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SELF-TRUST AND PARENTAL SUPPORT WITH ENTERPRENEURIAL MOTIVATION OF STUDENTS IN CLASS XI AUTOMATION EXPERTISE AND OFFICE MANAGEMENT PROGRAM AT SMK N 2 MAGELANG

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Abstract: The purpose of this study is to determine the relationship between self-confidence and parental support with entrepreneurial motivation in class XI students of automation and governance expertise program offices of SMK N 2 Magelang. This study used a sample of 102 students. The technique used in data collection in this study is to use saturated samples with a questionnaire or a questionnaire that contains three variables, namely self-confidence, parental support, and entrepreneurial motivation. The results of the study are to show there is a positive and significant relationship between self-confidence and parental support for the entrepreneurial motivation of students at SMK N 2 Magelang.

Keywords: *Confidence, Parental Support, Entrepreneurial Motivation*

1. Introduction

The difficulty of job opportunities in the current pandemic has caused serious problems for job seekers. The existing job vacancies are not equal to the number of job seekers, which results in a high unemployment rate. Many factors cause poverty in Indonesia still high, including the high unemployment rate. Various efforts have been made by the government to alleviate poverty and unemployment, where there is PKH (Family Hope Program), PNPM (National Community Empowerment Program), and many others. The government also established SMK (Vocational High School) which aims to produce a generation who has special skills so that it is expected that when they graduate they are experienced and skilled at work. However, currently, the number of unemployed SMK graduates is still relatively high.

Based on data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) according to the education received, from 9.77 million open unemployment rate, 13.55% SMK graduates, 9.86% SMA graduates, 8.08% graduates diploma, 7.35% university graduates, 6.46% junior high school graduates, and 3.61% elementary school graduates. December 2020 education level of the number of unemployed. Based on the main contributor rate data open unemployment came from SMK graduates, which amounted to 13.55%.

Semarang Bisnis (8 December 2020) Head of Training and Productivity The Disnakertrans division of Central Java Province explained that the industrial needs in Central Java are still not well accommodated properly in majors at SMK. Not only skill competence which is not appropriate, according to him, SMK graduates are also less equipped with soft skills to face the world of work. In addition, during this pandemic, many industrial levels reduced the workforce due to the impact of the pandemic, so that those who graduated from vocational high schools had difficulty finding jobs according to the competencies they had from school.

Vocational secondary education is education at the secondary education level that prioritizes the development of students' abilities to carry out certain types of work. Vocational secondary education prioritizes preparing students to enter the workforce and developing professional attitudes. Following its form, vocational high schools organize educational programs tailored to the types of work fields (Government Regulation Number 29 of 1990). SMK has many skill programs. The expertise program implemented at SMK adapts to the needs of the existing work world. The expertise program at the SMK level also adapts to the demands of the community and the market.

Maulida (2012), the education of students in vocational high schools can no longer only prepare ready-made workers in the business and industrial world. Students whose competencies have been upgraded according to the needs of the world of work need to also be equipped with entrepreneurial skills so that they can be independent. Entrepreneurship is a business activity that involves the ability to see business opportunities which then organize, organize, take risks, and develop the business created to gain profit. (Jailani, 2019). To foster entrepreneurial enthusiasm or desire, there must be motivation within these students to become entrepreneurial.

Entrepreneurial motivation where conditions encourage, drive and direct the desire of individuals to carry out entrepreneurial activities, in an independent way, believe in themselves, are future-oriented, dare to take risks, are creative, and highly value the desire for innovation (Ratnawati & Kuswardani, 2010). According to Wikanso (2013), in the context of entrepreneurship, motivation can be said to be the overall power the driving force in an entrepreneur that gives rise to entrepreneurial activities ensure the continuity of entrepreneurial activities and that give direction to activities entrepreneur so that the desired goals can be achieved.

Hamzah (2008) states that the category of motivation theory is based on: 1) satisfaction theory / *content theory*, 2) *process theory*. The theory of motivation based on content (content) focuses on needs and goals that include; need, desire, or urge to do an activity. Meanwhile, process-based motivation theory deals with how people behave and why they behave in certain ways. Conjunction with this research, then that will be used as a reference is the theory of motivation-based process (*process theory*).

According to Susanto (2009), one of the driving factors for entrepreneurship is personal factors. The personal factor that is considered important must be possessed by an entrepreneur is an attitude of self-confidence. (*Self-confidence self-confidence*) plays a very important role in one's success in life. A person may miss valuable opportunities due to insecurity. Not being confident is wrong the single biggest obstacle to action. Insecure

people are not only hesitant to act or they may not act at all. Many people have great potential in themselves, but that potential is not developed or exploited because they do not have self-confidence. (Hulukati, 2016). So that self-confidence and independence are important things to support entrepreneurial success.

Self-confidence is a self-assessment of one's ability to organize and carry out the actions needed to achieve the specified performance (Hidayat, 2011: 156) in Ramadhania (2018). According to King (2012: 153) in Ramadhania (2018), self-confidence is the belief that a person can control a situation and produce various positive results. Self-confidence is also known as self-esteem or self-image. Self-confidence brings power in managing the steps of an individual. Lauster (2002) in Ulfa (2019) argues that there are several aspects of self-confidence, including 1) Personal abilities, 2) Social interactions, and 3) Self-concept. Not having confidence in yourself is one of the biggest obstacles to action. Insecure people are not only hesitant to act or they may not act at all. Many people have great potential in themselves, but that potential is not developed or exploited because they do not have self-confidence. (Hulukati, 2016). So that self-confidence and independence are important things to support entrepreneurial success.

According to Wibowo (2011) in Wijaya, et al. (2018) the factor for the emergence of interest in entrepreneurship is the family environment, especially parents, the family environment is a group of people consisting of fathers, mothers, children, and other members of the family. This environment is the basis for the development and growth of children, which gives the first influence on the formation of personality, creativity and a sense of responsibility can be taught as early as possible when children begin to interact with adults.

According to Slameto (2010: 61) in Mahendra (2017), the family (parents) is the main and most important educational institution. The level of learning motivation that students have also depended on the level of attention and support of parents for entrepreneurial motivation (Mahendra, 2017). In the family environment, parents have an important role in creating a harmonious balance of relationships in the family. It is said that because if a family is harmonious in which there is a real, regular, and good relationship, a relationship with parents, the intensity of the parents in guiding their children increases. House (Smet, 1994) in Listiyani (2019) distinguishes four aspects of parental social support, namely: 1) Emotional Support, 2) Appreciation Support, 3) Instrumental Support, and 4) Informative Support.

The influence of parenting styles of parents who always spoil their children will affect the child's development. Children will grow up always relying on the dependence on their parents so that children will grow less confident and not creative so that the entrepreneurial spirit of students will be lacking. Likewise, when parents educate their children to be independent and creative, it will help the child's development to be independent and creative. So that it will encourage students to become entrepreneurs.

2. Research Method

In this study, the measurement was carried out on the real situation as seen by the respondent. This research is categorized into survey research. Survey research is the

acquisition of information from respondents collected by using a questionnaire. The instrument in this study was to measure self-confidence (X1), parental support (X2), and entrepreneurial motivation (Y).

Figure 1.
Thinking Framework

In this study, the researcher took the population from class XI of the office automation expertise and office management program of the Vocational High School 2 Magelang. How to determine the sample in this study using *saturated samples*, so that the sample in this study amounted to 102 students of class XI of the automation expertise and office management program of Vocational High School 2 Magelang.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Results

Table 1.
Results of Correlation Coefficient Analysis of

	Motivation Entrepreneurial(Y)	Confidence Self(X1)	Support Parental(X2)
Entrepreneurial Motivation (Y)			
<i>Pearson Correlation</i>		,636	,359
<i>Sig.</i>		,000	,000
Self Confidence (X1)			
<i>Pearson Correlation</i>	,636		
<i>Sig.</i>	,000		
Parental Support (X2)			
<i>Pearson Correlation</i>	,359		
<i>Sig.</i>	,000		

Source of data processed in 2021

Based on the calculation of research data, it is known that the correlation coefficient is 0.636 ($p < 0.05$), which means that there is a positive and significant relationship between self-confidence and entrepreneurial motivation. So that there is a positive relationship between self-confidence and entrepreneurial motivation towards students of SMK N 2 Magelang where the higher the self-confidence of the students of SMK N 2 Magelang, the

higher the entrepreneurial motivation for these students, and vice versa if the lower the level of self-confidence possessed by students of SMK N 2 Magelang, the lower entrepreneurial motivation within them. Thus the hypothesis proposed in this study is accepted.

The results of further analysis to determine the relationship between entrepreneurial motivation and parental support where the correlation coefficient between the two variables is 0.359 ($p < 0.05$). The results of this analysis indicate that there is a positive relationship between parental support and entrepreneurial motivation among students of SMK N 2 Magelang. Thus, the higher the parental support provided to the child, the higher the entrepreneurial motivation for vocational school students, conversely the lower the support given by parents, the lower the entrepreneurial motivation for students of SMK N 2 Magelang.

3.2. Discussion

The Positive Relationship Between Self-Confidence and Entrepreneurial Motivation

Self-confidence is one aspect of personality in the form of an individual's self-confidence and abilities so that it is not easy to be influenced by others and can act according to their will, be happy, optimistic, tolerant, and quite responsible. (*Self-confidence self-confidence*) plays a very important role in one's success in life. A person may miss valuable opportunities due to insecurity. Insecure people are not only hesitant to act or they may not act at all. Many people have great potential in themselves, but that potential is not developed or utilized because they do not have a level of self-confidence. So that self-confidence and independence are important things to support entrepreneurial success. The results showed that there was a positive and significant relationship between self-confidence and entrepreneurial motivation. This study supports Maulida (2012) previous research which is about self-confidence in increasing entrepreneurial motivation. The results show that self-confidence has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurial motivation. that entrepreneurial success is related to personality traits such as self-motivation. Entrepreneurial motivation is a condition that encourages, moves, and directs the desire of individuals to carry out entrepreneurial activities, in an independent way, believes in themselves, is future-oriented, dares to take risks, is creative, and highly assesses the desire for innovation Ratnawati & Kuswardani (2010). Many factors motivate a person to become entrepreneurial.

Thus the higher the self-confidence possessed by students of SMK N 2 Magelang, the higher the entrepreneurial motivation of these students, and vice versa if the lower the level of self-confidence possessed by students of SMK N 2 Magelang, the lower it will be. entrepreneurial motivation within them.

The Positive Relationship Between Parental Support and Entrepreneurial Motivation

Family (parents) are the main and foremost educational institutions. The level of learning motivation that students have also depended on the level of attention and support of parents for entrepreneurial motivation (Mahendra, 2017). The influence of parenting styles of parents who always spoil their children will affect the child's development. Children will grow up always relying on the dependence on their parents so that children

will grow less confident and not creative so that the entrepreneurial spirit of students will be lacking. Likewise, when parents educate their children to be independent and creative, it will help the child's development to be independent and creative. So that it will encourage students to become entrepreneurs.

The results show that there is a positive and significant relationship between parental support and entrepreneurial motivation. In line with the results of research by Mahendra, et. al (2017) and Maulida (2012). where the attention of parents to students by supporting entrepreneurship means that parents provide full support for their children in entrepreneurship both morally and materially.

The first and foremost parental support in determining student success in achieving goals, in this case, is entrepreneurship. The higher the parental support for entrepreneurial motivation, the higher the student's success in entrepreneurship and vice versa. Parental support is assistance provided by parents to children consisting of information or advice which can be in the form of verbal or non-verbal which makes the child feel cared for, appreciated, and loved.

4. Conclusion

There is a positive relationship between self-confidence and entrepreneurial motivation towards students of SMK N 2 Magelang where the higher the self-confidence of the students of SMK N 2 Magelang, the higher the motivation to be entrepreneurial in these students, and vice versa. if the lower the level of self-confidence possessed by students of SMK N 2 Magelang, the lower the entrepreneurial motivation will be in them. And there is a positive relationship between parental support and entrepreneurial motivation in students of SMK N 2 Magelang. Thus, the higher the parental support provided to the child, the higher the entrepreneurial motivation for vocational school students, conversely the lower the support given by parents, the lower the entrepreneurial motivation for students of SMK N 2 Magelang.

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